
FACTORS AFFECTING PHYSICAL WELLNESS AMONG TERTIARY STUDENT IN GORDON COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

Physical wellness is a crucial component of a student's overall well-being and significantly impacts how well they do in school and how happy they are. To understand the difficulties, they encounter and possible solutions, this study explores the many elements that affect the physical wellness of Gordon College's tertiary students. The study found several important elements that impacted Gordon College tertiary students' physical welfare. Physical activity was a key factor, and students who exercise regularly reported feeling physically better. The importance of dietary habits was discovered, and a balanced diet and enough water consumption are favorably correlated with well-being.

Keywords: Physical Wellness, Exercise, Factors, Height, Weight, Body Mass Index (BMI)

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INTRODUCTION

College Students contributions to an Institution are highly significant factors in school performance. College Students must maintain academic standing associated with time management to continue their academic career (Macan et al.,1990). However, because of this pressure, the students experience various stressors such as yearly tuition fees, academic competition, tons of requirements, time management, and personal issues (Neibling & Heckert 1999; Fogle & Pettijohn, 2013). These stressors may lead to extreme amounts of stress over a long period of time. Stress is often described as a feeling of being overwhelmed, worried, or run down. Stress can affect people of all ages, genders, and circumstances and can lead to both physical and psychological health issues.

College students cannot really find the time to exercise because of loaded requirements, feeling tired, and lack of time (Reichert et al., 2005). The nature of this dedication required to manage such demanding schedules, along with the growing health benefits of physical activity (Darren, 2006).

As a result, most of the students have physical inactivity or “sitting disease” that leads to slower blood flow, the feeling of fatigue, and risk for diabetes, chronic back pain, and risk of heart attack (Hoeger et al., 2017; Pajović et al.,2014). Furthermore, regular exercise

can improve sleep patterns, and immune function, reduce mental stress and anxiety, and most importantly, treat mild and moderate depression.

Kennedy, (2013) suggests that “physical fitness” is not only the most important key to a healthy body; it is the basis of dynamic and “creative intellectual” activity.

Another problem that occurs among college students is their unhealthy lifestyle (Brunt & Rhee, 2008).

College students affect their dietary habits negatively when they are away from the family (Brunt & Rhee, 2008). In the same manner, Dr. Augusto Litonjua, president of the Philippine Center for Diabetes Education Foundation blamed the “fast-food culture” for offering calorie-dense food, which leads to obesity and a higher risk for diabetes.

This undertaking might make it possible to know the factors affecting the physical wellness among college students at Gordon College.

The researcher aims to investigate the significance of differences when grouped based on demographic factors namely: age, sex, height, weight, body mass index (BMI), and College Department.

Review of Related Literature

Increased implementation of technology will increase students' comprehension of content and the development of skills in such areas as analytical reasoning, problem-solving, information evaluation, and creative thinking. In KSA, there is a dire dearth and paucity of information regarding the effect of technology usage on learning achievement. Rather, studies conducted within KSA have found that students are used to a comparatively more traditional learning model. However, the comprehensive use of technology would create a good environment that facilitates of learning. This approach would shift education from the classical approach (which has not prioritized students' pursuit of understanding) toward the deep-meaning approaches that would help students seek a true understanding of the central principles, themes, and applications of any given area of study. Using technology would support the active learning of students in an educational environment designed to help students achieve meaningful learning – which, in turn, could result in positive, cumulatively progressive gains in learning outcomes (Al-Hariri & Al-Hattami, 2017).

Compared to students who lived off-campus, those who lived on campus consumed a larger variety of fruits, vegetables, and dairy products. Those who lived off-campus consumed less variety of grains compared to those who lived with parents (Brunt & Rhee, 2008). There are a variety of predictors of obesity including genetics, physical activity, and food consumption and there are other outcomes of food choice and nutrition that also have an independent effect on health including some types of cancer, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes (Deshpande et al, 2009).

The present study examined perceived stress, health habits, and daily hassles and uplifts among 135 college freshmen. We hypothesized that students with lower stress levels would be male, would have better self-care health habits, would experience fewer minor medical health issues, would have higher academic performance, and would experience fewer daily hassles and more daily uplifts than students who experienced high perceived stress (Fogle, 2013).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design with the questionnaire as the main instrument for gathering data to determine the factors affecting physical wellness among college students at Gordon College. Descriptive research describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. The objective of the descriptive study is to identify the present condition, examine the relationship of traits and characteristics, and interpret the result with the used of statistical calculations.

According to Manuel and Medel (1998) and Asio (2021), descriptive research describes what is involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or processes of phenomena.

Fowler (2009) said that in survey method research, participants answer questions administered through interviews or questions. Questions should be written so they are clear and easy to comprehend. He also added that many researchers prefer to use a Likert-type scale because it's very easy to analyze statistically.

Respondents

The total sample size was 282, and they came from different college departments accessible to the researcher.

The total population of the midyear class Academic Year 2018-2019 was 1063. This Sample Size Calculator is presented as a public service of Creative Research Systems survey software. The confidence level is 95% and the confidence interval is 5%.

The study employed the stratified sampling technique to select the college student respondents. Stratified sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller groups known as strata.

The researcher coordinated with different departments that cater to tertiary-level students and conducted the survey. The respondents were the college students available at the time of the survey.

Instrument of the Study

The main instrument for gathering data in this study was the questionnaire. It was composed of 2 main parts. The first part is all about the demographic profile of the respondents which describes their student-related factors: age, sex, height, weight, Body Mass Index (BMI), and college department. The second part determined the factors affecting the physical wellness of 3rd year students including exercise, diet, substance, technology, stress management, environment, lifestyle, and medical care. The respondents answered always, often, seldom, sometimes, and never.

The self-constructed questionnaire was drafted based on the gathered materials from related literature and studies. It was submitted to the adviser for confirmation, correction, and suggestions. After the correction and revision of the questionnaire, was presented again to the adviser for final approval before it was administered to the respondents. The

questionnaire was pilot-tested to twenty students (20) of Senior High School who were not the direct respondents of the study for validation of the instrument.

Statistical Analysis

The Weighted Mean was employed to determine the factors affecting physical wellness and show which of the rating scales gathered the highest score.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the distribution of tertiary students according to age. There were two hundred twenty-seven (227) or 80.5 percent under the age group of 18 – 21 years old while the oldest respondents who comprised the least number of tertiary students were seven (7) or 2.5 percent under the age of 31 – 35 years old. The result only implies that the majority of the tertiary students in the late adolescence of Erik Erickson’s theory stages of human development.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-21 years old	227	80.5
22-26 years old	40	14.2
27-30 years old	8	2.8
31-35 years old	7	2.5
Sex		
Male	94	33.3
Female	188	66.7
Height (cm)		
122-135	1	0.4
136-149	19	6.7
150-163	161	57.1
164-177	91	32.3
178-191	10	3.5
Weight (kg)		
81.4-116.4	118	45.0
117.4-152.4	110	37.6
153.4-188.4	40	14.2
189.4-224.4	13	2.8
225.4-260.4	1	0.4
Total	282	100

The table also shows the distribution of Tertiary Students according to sex, there were one hundred eighty-eight (188) or 66.7 percent female college students and the male college students were ninety-four (94) or 33.3 percent. This result is also affirmed by the study conducted by Neisen, Larsen, and LaFontaine (2012) wherein 53.3% of the respondents were female and the remaining 46.7% were males.

Furthermore, the distribution of tertiary students according to height. There were one hundred sixty-one (161) or 57.1 percent under the height group of 150-163 centimeters while the respondents who comprised the least number of tertiary students was one (1) or 0.4 percent under the height group 122-135 centimeters. The result is similar to the study conducted by Murray (2009), wherein the normal height of Filipinos is relatively 160 – 162 cm.

Lastly, the table shows the distribution of tertiary students according to weight. There were one hundred eighteen (118) or 45.0 percent under the weight group of 81.4-116.4 pounds while the respondents who comprised the least number of tertiary students was one (1) or .4 percent under the weight group 225.4-260.4 pounds. The result only implies that the majority of the tertiary students similar to D.R Miller Formula (1983) wherein the ideal body weight for men should be 52 kilograms at 52 feet and for women should be 49 kilograms and 1.7 kilograms added for every five inches more.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Respondents According to Weight

Weight	Frequency	Percentage
81.4 – 116.4	118	45.0
117.4 – 152.4	110	37.6
153.4 – 188.4	40	14.2
189.4 – 224.4	13	2.8
225.4-260.4	1	0.4
Total	282	100.0

Table 2 shows the distribution of tertiary students according to weight. There were one hundred eighteen (118) or 45.0 percent under the weight group of 81.4-116.4 pounds while the respondents who comprised the least number of tertiary students was one (1) or .4 percent under the weight group 225.4-260.4 pounds. The result only implies that the majority of the tertiary students similar to the D.R Miller Formula (1983) wherein the ideal body weight for men should be 52 kilograms at 52 feet and for women should be 49 kilograms and 1.7 kilograms added for every five inches more.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to BMI

BMI	Frequency	Percentage
14-18.4 "underweight"	46	16.3
18.5-24.9 "normal"	171	60.6
25.0-29.9 "overweight"	45	16.0
30.0-34.9 "class I obesity"	13	4.6
35.0-39.9 "class II obesity"	5	1.8
40.0-100 "class III obesity"	2	0.7
Total	282	100.0

Table 3 shows the distribution of tertiary students according to Body Mass Index. There were one hundred eighteen (171) or 60.6 percent under the BMI group of 18.5-24.9, classified as normal while the respondents who comprised the least number of tertiary

students was one (1) or .4 percent under the weight group 225.4-260.4 pounds classified as class III obesity. The same results in the study conducted by Catequista & Uy (2014) found that the majority of adolescents have normal body mass index.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Department

Department	Frequency	Percentage
College of Education Arts and Sciences (CEAS)	129	45.7
College of Business and Accountancy (CBA)	49	17.4
College of Hospitality and Tourism Management (CHTM)	53	18.8
College of Computer Studies (CCS)	32	11.3
College of Allied Health and Studies (CAHS)	19	6.7
Total	282	100.0

Table 4 shows the distribution of Tertiary students according to department. The majority of the Tertiary students were under the College of Education Arts and Sciences (CEAS) one hundred twenty-nine (129) or 45.7 percent and while the least of the respondents under the College of Allied Health and Studies (CAHS) nineteen (19) or 6.7 The rest of the respondents were below fifty-three (53) or 18.8 under the College of Hospitality and Tourism Management (CHTM), College of Business and Accountancy (CBA) forty-nine (49) or 17.4 percent, and College of Computer Studies (CCS) thirty-two (32) or 11.3 percent. The results indicate that the majority of the college students at Gordon College are interested in the teaching profession because education is one of the in-demand and priority courses for 2014 - 2018 according to the Commission on Higher Education.

Table 5. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Exercise

Exercise	Mean	Interpretation
1) I engage myself in any kinds of exercise.	3.45	Often
2) I find ways to exercise even with heavy schedule.	2.84	Seldom
3) I engage in a 10-minute low intensity exercises every other day (walking, jogging and dance workout).	3.33	Seldom
4) I maintain moderate intensity exercise 30-minute a day 3 days a week (walking, jogging and dance work out).	2.93	Seldom
5) I attend workout at the gym 30-40 minutes a day three times per week.	2.01	Sometimes
6) I feel better after doing exercise.	3.78	Often
7) I am willing to undergo rigid exercise if it is necessary.	3.59	Often
Overall Mean	3.13	Seldom

Table 5 shows the weighted mean and descriptive rating of factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary-level students in Gordon College in terms of Exercise. An analysis of the data conveys the information that the highest respondents rated was Indicator 6 “I feel better after doing exercise” which has a weighted mean of 3.78. This result corresponds to the findings of Hassmén, P., Koivula, N., & Uutela, A. (2000). Their study revealed that there is a connection between physical exercise and psychological well-

being. The study emphasized that those individuals who engage in regular exercise feel better about their fitness and health as well as experience less depression and anger. Furthermore, the least rated in terms of exercise was Indicator 5 “I attend workout at the gym 30-40 minutes a day three times per week” has a weighted mean of 2.01. They perceive factors affecting physical wellness through exercise as seldom with overall mean of 3.13. The result implies that the study of Reichert et al., (2003) found that the barriers to participation in any physical activity were lack of time, lack of company, lack of money, and feeling too tired.

Table 6. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Diet

Diet	Mean	Interpretation
1) I eat different varieties of vegetables each week.	3.76	Often
2) I prefer fish than red meat in my meals.	3.39	Seldom
3) I lessen the intake of junk foods.	3.42	Often
4) I refrain from eating in fast food.	2.97	Seldom
5) I avoid eating junk foods or low nutrition foods.	3.11	Seldom
6) I avoid eating packed, canned or ready to eat foods.	2.98	Seldom
7) I refrain from eating fatty foods.	3.06	Seldom
Overall Mean	3.24	Seldom

Table 6 shows the mean distribution of the factors affecting physical wellness in terms of diet. In particular, the highest distribution of mean was Indicator 1 “I eat different varieties of vegetables each week” with a mean of 3.76. Furthermore, analyzing data Indicator 4 “I refrain from eating fast food” with mean of 2.97 got the lowest score. In general, the respondent's overall mean 3.24 interpreted as seldom. This result contradicts to the study of Acampado and Valenzuela (2018) about the dietary habits of Filipino college students, the study conveyed those one of every three students in each year level had below average to poor dietary habits, which means they seldom eat proper types of foods.

Table 7. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in terms of Substance

Substance	Mean	Interpretation
1) I avoid excessive intake of caffeine.	3.66	Often
2) I avoid excessive drinking of alcohol.	4.02	Often
3) I don't smoke.	4.44	Always
4) I avoid taking non-prescribed drugs.	4.36	Always
5) I refrain from the use of any harmful substance.	4.37	Always
6) I drink energy drink (sting, cobra, monster and red bull) moderately.	3.11	Seldom
7) I don't smoke marijuana or other relative substances.	3.06	Always
Overall Mean	4.09	Often

Table 7 shows the weighted mean and descriptive rating of factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary-level student in Gordon College in terms of Substance. An analysis of the data conveys the information that the highest respondents rated was Indicator 7 “I don't smoke marijuana or other relative substances” with a weighted mean of 4.64. The

lowest respondents rated was Indicator 6 “I drink energy drink (sting, cobra, monster and Red Bull) moderately” with a weighted mean of 3.11. In general, the respondent's overall mean was 4.09 with the descriptor of often. These results imply that the respondents are aware of the act of instituting the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002, repealing Republic Act No. 6425, otherwise known as the Dangerous Drugs Act of 1972, wherein it is the policy of the State to safeguard the integrity of its territory and the well-being of its citizenry particularly the youth, from the harmful effects of dangerous drugs on their physical and mental well-being.

Table 8. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Technology

Technology	Mean	Interpretation
1) I can learn technology easily.	4.13	Often
2) I used computer technology for school requirements if it is necessary.	4.40	Always
3) I use computer.	4.33	Always
4) I am satisfied using modern technology every day.	4.23	Always
5) I am motivated to find ways to use technology in school requirements.	4.29	Always
6) I felt very confident using technology.	4.04	Often
7) Technological advances make my life better as college student.	4.34	Always
Total	4.25	Always

Table 8 shows the mean distribution of the factors affecting physical wellness in terms of technology. In particular, the highest distribution of mean was Indicator 2 “I used computer technology for school requirements if it is necessary” with a mean of 4.40. Furthermore, the lowest score was Indicator 6 “I felt very confident using technology” with a mean of 4.04. In general, the respondents' overall mean was 4.25, which is interpreted as always. The results are connected to the study of Al-Hariri and Al-Hattami (2016), who investigate the relationship between students' use of technology and their academic achievement in physiological courses. The study demonstrates that the most used devices are laptops (50%) and phones (42%), followed by tablets (7%) and desktop computers (0.5%). They found out that the use of technology increases the academic achievements of physiology students at the University of Dammam.

Table 9 shows the weighted mean and descriptive rating of factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary-level students in Gordon College in terms of stress management. An analysis of the data conveys the information that the highest respondents rated was Indicator 6 “I have fighting spirit to positively solve my problems (financial, school requirements, peer and personal issue).” with a weighted mean of 4.11. The lowest respondents rated it as Indicator 4: “I perform well in the classroom even if I’m stressed.” It had a weighted mean of 3.45. In general, the respondent's overall mean was 3.82 with the descriptor of often. The results connected to the study of Menguito and Calleja (2010) wherein they analyze the negative connotations of “*bahala na*,” whereas it has a positive

view which most observe in a poor family used in the context of courage, hope Self-efficacy and search for the sacred that leads to attaining series of goals.

Table 9. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Stress Management

Stress Management	Mean	Interpretation
1) I am able to manage my emotions in times of stress.	3.62	Often
2) I can easily recover from stress in my academic requirements.	3.59	Often
3) I prepare myself in any stress situation.	3.69	Often
4) I perform well in classroom even if I am stressed.	3.45	Often
5) I don't give up easily in my life because of my problems (financial, school requirements, peer and personal issue).	4.10	Often
6) I have fighting spirit to positively solve my problems (financial, school requirements, peer and personal issue).	4.11	Often
7) I take time to have some fun at least three times a week.	4.09	Often
8) I practice stress management as necessary.	3.90	Often
Overall Mean	3.82	Often

Table 10. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Environment

Environment	Mean	Interpretation
1) I practice the 3R's (reduce, reuse and recycling) to help the environment.	3.77	Often
2) I avoid using disposable plastic bags.	3.42	Often
3) I used reusable bags in shopping instead of disposable plastic bags.	3.54	Often
4) I strictly follow the policy of "no styro foam and plastic bags allowed" inside the school.	3.67	Often
5) I strictly follow the policy of proper disposal of garbage in our barangay.	3.85	Often
6) I am willing to commit myself in any environmental health seminar in our barangay.	3.74	Often
7) I am willing to be part of an organization to fight for clearer and better environment.	3.83	Often
8) I can contribute my skills for the environmental program of the school.	3.83	Often
9) I do not expose myself to any chemical and electromagnetic toxins.	3.82	Often
Total	3.72	Often

Table 10 shows the weighted mean and descriptive rating of factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary-level students in Gordon College in terms of environment. An analysis of the data conveys the information that the highest respondents rated was Indicator 5 "I

strictly follow the policy of proper disposal of garbage in our barangay.” with a weighted mean of 3.85. The lowest respondents rated it as Indicator 2: “I avoid using disposable plastic bags.”

Table 11. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Lifestyle

Lifestyle	Mean	Interpretation
1) I organize my time every day.	3.98	Often
2) I have a positive mind each day.	3.88	Often
3) I read a daily newspaper to keep me informed of what is going in the outside world.	3.11	Seldom
4) I read books every day.	3.14	Seldom
5) I sleep 5-8 hours each night.	3.66	Often
6) I drink 6-8 glasses of water a day.	3.66	Often
7) I treat myself to an expensive restaurant as a reward to my achievement.	3.33	Seldom
8) I schedule periodic massage to maintain good health.	2.81	Seldom
Total	3.42	Often

Table 11 shows the mean distribution of the factors affecting physical wellness in terms of lifestyle. In particular, the highest distribution of mean was Indicator 1 “I organize my time every day.” with a mean of 3.98. Moreover, the lowest score was Indicator 1 “I schedule a periodic massage to maintain good health” with a mean of 2.81. In general, the respondent's overall mean was 3.42, which was interpreted as seldom. Macan et al. emphasized that the performance of the students is highly associated with how they can control and manage their time.

Table 12. Factors Affecting Physical Wellness in Terms of Medical Care

Lifestyle	Mean	Interpretation
1. I maintain monthly medical check-up.	2.67	Seldom
2. I am able to get medical care easily if necessary.	3.30	Seldom
3. I have easy access to any medical specialist.	3.09	Seldom
4. I seek medical advice when any symptoms of ailment are present.	3.24	Seldom
5. Doctors assess me patiently and in a courteous manner.	3.42	Often
6. I am contented with the medical care I receive.	3.52	Often
7. Doctor, nurse or other medical practitioners carefully treat and examine me.	3.55	Often
8. I can easily get access to any free medical check-up in the barangay.	3.27	Seldom
Total	3.27	Seldom

Table 12 shows the mean distribution of the factors affecting physical wellness in terms of medical care. In particular, the highest distribution of mean was Indicator 7 “Doctor, nurse or other medical practitioner carefully treat and examine me” with the mean of 3.55.

Furthermore, the lowest score was Indicator 1 “I maintain monthly medical check-up.” with the mean of 4.04. In general, the respondents overall mean was 3.26 interpreted as seldom. The results agree to the study of Beach et al. (2006) wherein all illness and healing processes were found in relationship-centred care principles (1) that relationships in health care ought to include the personhood of the participants, (2) Feelings and Emotions of the patient are highly significant (3) all health care practitioner relationship to the participants concede mutual (4) The relationship of health care practitioner to the patient morally valuable.

Table 13. The Results of Kruskal-Wallis Tests to Compare the Level in Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on Age

Factors	Mean Rank	x²	p-value
Exercise	127.64	2.146	.543
Diet	140.25	0.160	.984
Substance	136.97	6.291	.098
Technology	136.82	5.705	.127
Stress Management	147.86	4.949	.176
Environment	138.25	1.225	.747
Lifestyle	129.98	2.317	.509
Medical Care	123.87	4.527	.210

Note: N=282; df=3

The table shows the results of Kruskal-Wallis test on factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary student-respondents when grouped according to their age. There is no statistically significant difference that was observed for exercise, $x^2 = 2.146$ with probability values of 0.543; for diet, $x^2 = 0.160$ with a probability values of 0.984. All of the obtained values were greater than the alpha significant level set at 0.05. This means that we accept the null hypothesis. These findings are similar to the study conducted by Steven McPartland (2013) about Stress, Lifestyle, and Diet in College Students: Analysis of the YEAH Study. He found out that there were no significant differences in age or year in school between the male and female subjects.

Table 14. The Results of Mann-Whitney U to Compare the Level in Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on Sex

	Sex	Mean Rank	U	W	Z	p-value
Exercise	Male	159.03	7188	24954	-2.556*	.011
	Female	132.73				
Substance	Male	116.82	6516	10981	-3.605*	.000
	Female	153.74				
Diet	Male	146.57	8359	26125	-0.740	.459
	Female	138.96				
Technology	Male	148.35	8192	25298	-1.004	.315
	Female	138.07				
Stress Management	Male	144.78	8528	26294	-.479	.632
	Female	139.86				

Note: * $p < .05$

Table 14 shows the significant differences found in terms of exercise in factors affecting the physical wellness in terms of sex between male and female college students in Gordon College. Particularly, male respondents exhibit higher in exercise (mean rank= 159.03) compared to female respondents (mean rank= 132.73) ($U = 7188$, $W = 24954$, $Z = -2.556$, $p = .011 < 0.05$). The result is similar to the study conducted by Gonçalves, Costa & Gomes (2011) that male student has higher tendency to engage in exercise. Female adolescents were more likely to exercise occasionally, whereas males were more likely to exercise regularly.

Another significant difference found in terms of substance using the Mann-Whitney U to compare the level in factors affecting the Physical wellness of male and female respondents. Specifically, female shows higher in substance (mean rank = 153.84) compared to male students (mean rank = 116.82) ($U= 6516$, $W = 10981$, $Z = -3.605$, $p = . < 001$). The results contradict to the study of Wilsnack et, al (1997-2007) high-volume drinking was consistently more prevalent among men than among women, but lifetime abstention from alcohol was consistently more prevalent among women. Furthermore, women in all age groups were consistently more likely to have stopped drinking than men. It can be gleaned from the table that there is no statistically significant difference that was observed for diet $p= 0.459$, technology $p = 0.315$, stress management $p = 0.632$, environment $p = 0.304$, lifestyle $p = 0.267$ and medical care $p = 0.868$ with the probability values of greater than the alpha significant level $p = >0.05$.

Table 15. The Results of Kruskal-Wallis Tests to Compare the Level of Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on Height

Factors	Mean Rank	χ^2	p-value
Exercise	152.24	3.472	.482
Diet	162.03	5.344	.254
Substance	164.11	9.380	.052
Technology	136.56	3.551	.470
Stress Management	150.95	8.718	.069
Environment	150.73	7.351	.110
Lifestyle	130.87	4.510	.341
Medical Care	131.35	2.325	.676

Note: $N= 282$; $df= 4$

The table shows the results of Kruskal-Wallis H test on factors affecting physical wellness of tertiary student-respondents when grouped according to their height. It can be gleaned from the table that there is no significant differences. Since the following results were obtained: for exercise ($\chi^2= 3.472$, $p= 0.482$), Diet ($\chi^2= 5.344$, $p= 0.254$), substance ($\chi^2= 9.380$, $p= 0.052$), technology ($\chi^2= 3.551$, $p = .470$), stress management ($\chi^2= 8.718$, $p = 0.069$), environment ($\chi^2= 7.531$, $p= 0.110$), lifestyle ($\chi^2= 4.510$, $p= .341$), medical care ($\chi^2= 2.325$, $p= 0.676$). All of the obtained values were greater than the alpha sig. level set at 0.05 therefore the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 16 shows the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test on factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary student respondents when grouped according to their weight. It can be gleaned from the table that there are no statistically significant differences that were observed for exercise $p= 0.357$, diet $p= 0.261$, technology $p= 0.982$, stress management $p= 0.478$, environment $p= 0.78$, lifestyle $p= 0.418$ and medical care $p= 0.635$ with the probability value of greater than the alpha significant level at 0.05. This finding is similar to the study conducted by Gomes et al., (2011) about Exercise, eating disordered behaviors, and psychological well-being: a study with Portuguese adolescents. They found out that there are no statistically significant differences in physical activities in terms of desired ideal weight.

Table 16. The Results of Kruskal-Wallis Tests to Compare the Level in Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on Weight

Factors	Mean Rank	χ^2	<i>p</i>-value
Exercise	163.85	4.383	.357
Diet	155.73	4.261	.372
Substance	130.17	10.678*	.030
Technology	135.20	0.403	.982
Stress Management	168.63	3.497	.478
Environment	162.22	8.412	.078
Lifestyle	164.77	3.911	.418
Medical Care	161.77	2.555	.635

Note: $N= 282$; $df= 4$; * $p < .05$

The substance factor has a mean rank 130.17 with $\chi^2= 10.678$ with a corresponding probability of 0.030, which is significant at alpha 0.05. Findings revealed similar to the study of Eichen et, al. (2010) wherein they found that the use of substances affects the weight of adolescents.

Table 17. The Results of Kruskal-Wallis Tests to Compare the Level in Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on BMI

Factors	Mean Rank	χ^2	<i>p</i>-value
Exercise	147.92	8.277	.142
Diet	123.93	11.097*	.049
Substance	129.14	10.509	.062
Technology	121.19	8.700	.122
Stress Management	123.23	4.383	.496
Environment	124.61	3.553	.615
Lifestyle	128.05	7.495	.186
Medical Care	146.68	2.552	.769

Note: $N= 282$; $df= 5$; * $p < .05$

Table 17 shows the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test on factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary student-respondents when grouped according to their BMI. There is

a significant difference that was observed for diet, $\chi^2= 11.097$ with probability values of 0.049 is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This was further verified by the study of Spanos and Hankey (2010) wherein he found out that there is a significant relation between BMI and the dietary habits of college students.

It was also observed from the table the not significant variables since the following was obtained: exercise, $\chi^2= 8.277$, $p= 0.142$, substance $\chi^2= 10.509$, $p= 0.062$, technology $\chi^2 = 8.700$, $p= 0.122$, stress management $\chi^2= 4.383$, $p= 0.496$, environment $\chi^2= 3.553$, $p= 0.615$, lifestyle $\chi^2= 7.495$, $p= 0.186$, medical care $\chi^2= 2.552$, $p= 0.769$ with the probability value of greater than the alpha significant level at 0.05.

Table 18. The Results of Kruskal-Wallis Tests to Compare the Level in Factors Affecting Physical Wellness Based on Department

Factors	Department	Mean Rank	χ^2	<i>p</i>
Substance	CEAS	158.89	20.261	.000**
	CBA	152.37		
	CHTM	117.20		
	CCS	125.25		
	CAHS	90.55		
Lifestyle	CEAS	117.33	27.849	.000**
	CBA	151.00		
	CHTM	153.79		
	CCS	195.30		
	CAHS	156.24		
Medical Care	CEAS	118.30	24.554	.000**
	CBA	155.03		
	CHTM	147.17		
	CCS	186.19		
	CAHS	173.03		
Exercise	CEAS	140.79	6.079	.193
	CBA	131.03		
	CHTM	133.13		
	CCS	172.81		
	CAHS	143.24		
Diet	CEAS	137.39	5.442	.245
	CBA	133.14		
	CHTM	139.82		
	CCS	172.22		
	CAHS	143.89		
Technology	CEAS	137.83	6.229	.183
	CBA	147.80		
	CHTM	134.43		
	CCS	170.41		
	CAHS	121.18		

Stress Management	CEAS	141.51	3.959	.412
	CBA	140.72		
	CHTM	134.53		
	CCS	164.88		
	CAHS	123.53		
Environment	CEAS	137.45	5.402	.248
	CBA	146.60		
	CHTM	128.80		
	CCS	168.66		
	CAHS	145.53		

*Note: N= 282; df= 4; *p < .05*

Table 18 shows the results of Kruskal-Wallis H test on factors affecting the physical wellness of tertiary student-respondents when grouped according to their BMI. There is significant difference that was observed for Substance, $\chi^2 = 20.261$ with probability values of 0.00 is significant at alpha = 0.05.

This means that null hypothesis is rejected. This is further verified by the study of Di Pietro, Giorgio et al., (2012) about the effect of alcohol and drug consumption on academic performance: a treatment effect evaluation. They found out that there is a significant negative impact for too much consumption of substance (marijuana, tobacco, cocaine and alcohol) in the academic achievement of the students.

There is also a significant difference occur in lifestyle factor with the probability of 0.00 is significant at alpha = 0.05. The results support the study of Welle and Graf (2013) wherein it was found out that stress affect the lifestyle of the college students.

Another significant difference in medical factor of college students with the probability values of 0.00 is significant at alpha = 0.05. This means that the null hypothesis was rejected and the hypothesis was accepted. This is further verified by the study of Grace (2010) wherein he found out that college students experience higher rates of medical issues that the general population.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the majority of college students fall within the young adulthood stage of Erikson's theory of human development, with a notable gender disparity favoring female students over their male counterparts. Furthermore, most tertiary students exhibited normal height, weight, and BMI, while the College of Education, Arts, and Sciences accounted for the largest portion of respondents. Interestingly, when college students were grouped by age and height, no significant differences were identified in the factors influencing physical wellness. However, it was evident that various factors, including exercise, substance use, diet, lifestyle choices, and access to medical care, played a significant role in shaping the physical wellness of college students. Contrary to the null hypothesis, the study's results indicated that significant differences did exist in these factors when students were categorized based on sex, weight, BMI, and academic

department, shedding light on important distinctions in the physical wellness experiences of college students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to foster a culture of holistic well-being among tertiary students, it is imperative that Gordon College, in collaboration with local government units and non-government organizations, organizes orientation and awareness programs. These initiatives should educate students on the significance of regular exercise in promoting a healthy lifestyle. Additionally, there is a pressing need to continually disseminate nutritional information, emphasizing the pivotal role that diet plays in providing the requisite strength and energy for active engagement both within and outside the educational institution. Furthermore, the school administration and college departments should jointly conduct orientation sessions to raise awareness about the importance of medical care, encouraging students to proactively seek healthcare when faced with health issues. Lastly, to enhance our comprehension of the wellness factors affecting college students, further research endeavors should be undertaken to validate results and refine our understanding of this crucial facet of student life.

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